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Research Article

ROLE OF CLINICAL PHARMACIST IN IDENTIFYING, REPORTING AND MANGEMENT OF POTENTIAL DRUG- DRUG INTERACTION AMONG PATIENTS ADMITTED IN INTENSIVE CARE UNIT

Asifmiya, Nameera Jahan, Shagufta Afreen

Rajiv Memorial Education Society's College Of Pharmacy Kalaburagi – 585102

Abstract:

Aim: The study aimed to assess the role of clinical pharmacists in identifying, reporting, and managing potential drug-drug interactions (DDIs) among ICU patients. With the increasing complexity of therapeutic regimens in critically ill patients, the risk of DDIs is increases, and the involvement of clinical pharmacists is crucial .**Methods and Materials:** A Prospective Interventional study is carried out for a period of 6 months in intensive care units of GIMS, Kalaburgi. The study is conducted by enrolling patients admitted to intensive care unit, by considering the study criteria. From the case sheets of the enrolled patient's demographic, data, reason for admission, co-morbidities, medical and medication history, medication chart is noted in a suitably designed data collection form. The DDIs is identified and analyzed by using Micromedex data base. The identified DDIs is brought to the notice of the physician/prescriber/PGs and possible measures is taken to avoid the interactions. The action taken by the physician/prescriber for the suggestions given by the clinical pharmacist to avoid the DDIs is also been noted. **Results.** Among a total of 177 patients included in study from the Intensive Care Unit (ICU) at GIMS hospital. The majority of the patients were male (55.9%), with a mean age of 52.25 years, and the most prevalent age group being 41-60 years. Hypertension (31.6%) and diabetes mellitus (18.1%) were the most common comorbidities. The average number of drugs prescribed per patient was 10.94, with 48% of patients receiving 5-10 drugs. The risk of DDIs increased with the number of medications prescribed. All 177 patients identified at least one DDI, with an average of 2.90 interactions per patient. The total number of identified DDIs was 514, with major interactions accounting for 47.86% of the cases. A significant proportion of DDIs were categorized as major (47.86%), followed by moderate (33.46%) and minor (18.6%) interactions. Common Drugs Involved in DDIs: Ondansetron , phenytoin, and furosemide were the most frequently interacting drugs, highlighting the importance of vigilant monitoring of these medications in ICU settings Study reveals that; there was statistically significant association of duration of hospital stays and DDI's . More number of days of hospital stays patients was observed more numbers of DDI's **conclusion:** The study concludes that the presence of a clinical pharmacist in the ICU can play a pivotal role in the early identification and management of potential DDIs, thus improving patient outcomes. The clinical pharmacist's interventions, including adjustments in drug regimens, dose alterations, and frequent monitoring, were essential in minimizing the adverse effects caused by DDIs. This collaborative approach between clinical pharmacists and physicians led to a more optimized and safer medication therapy

Corresponding author:**Mr.Riyaz Miya,**Rajiv Memorial Education Society's College Of Pharmacy,
Kalaburagi – 585102

QR CODE

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INTRODUCTION:**DRUG-DRUG INTERACTION:**

Drug-drug interactions are the pharmacological or clinical responses to the administration of drug combinations different from that anticipated from the known effects of the two agents when given alone. Some drug-drug interactions (DDIS) can result in toxicity, in an alteration of the desired therapeutic end point or at the very extreme in a life threatening situations^[101]

In every potential DDI an index drug and an interacting drug is involved. The drug for which the pharmacological or clinical response is altered is called the index drug, and the drug that induces the interaction is the interacting drug.^[2] Drug- drug interactions occur when two or more drugs react with each other. The effects of a drug are changed by the presence of another drug, resulting in synergistic, additive or antagonistic outcomes and are an important cause of preventable adverse drug events.^[102]

Clinically significant Interactions are often predictable and usually Undesired Adverse effects or Therapeutic failure may result. Rarely, clinicians can Use predictable drug-drug interactions to produce a Desired therapeutic effect^[103]

PHARMACOEPIDEMIOLOGY OF DDIs

About 5% of all adverse drug reactions in hospitals are caused by DDIs, and the majority of which are avoidable. With the increase in the number of patients, multiple diseases, and complex therapeutic regimens, poly-pharmacy becomes unavoidable in ICU. Polypharmacy increases the risks of drug AEs, especially the DBISs and that leads to elevated healthcare costs, morbidity and mortality, within the context of above facts, it is important to investigate potential DDIs in ICUs^[104]

The incidences of DDIS in different countries vary from 6% to 70% due to variability in methodologies and settings. Around 20% of hospitalized patients were susceptible to DDIS and the incidence was higher in patients with heart disease and elderly. About one-third of cancer patients are at risk of DDI.^[105] According to a recent review, around 0.6% of the hospital admissions, 0.1% of re-hospitalizations and 0.05% of the emergency department visits were caused due to adverse drug reactions as a result of DDIs.^[106]

According to a study carried out in Mexico City, 80.0% of ambulatory patients were found to have prescriptions with one or more potential DDIs and about 3.8% of patients were prescribed drugs with combinations that should be avoided due to interactions^[107]. A recent study conducted in the USA showed that 46.3% of ICU prescriptions

included pDDIs^[108], while Brazilian studies have reported a prevalence of 67% or 70%.^[109]

The highest risk for Dis occurs in those patients with advanced age, those taking more than 4 medications, or those taking medications with narrow therapeutic index, or requiring therapeutic drug monitoring the consequences of mistakes and drug errors such as drug interactions affect millions of patients every year and contribute to 5% of patient's admissions into hospitals.^[110]

FACTORS RESPONSIBLE FOR DRUG INTERACTIONS

- Genes
- Physiology
- Age
- Life style (diet ,exercise)
- Underlying disease
- Drug dose
- Duration of combined therapy
- The relative time of administration of the two substance (sometimes, interactions can be avoided if two drugs are taken at different time).^[111]

The majority of those interactions occurred because either prescriber do not consider them relevant or prescriber's knowledge of DDIS is generally poor. Hence they could be prevented through applying proper interventions. This can improve the quality of drug therapy and increase patient safety.^[112]

Concurrent administration of drugs is one factor that can alter the response to drugs. The drug interactions may be beneficial or harmful, depending on various factors related to the medication, the patient or the conditions under which the medication is used. Beneficial interactions can increase efficiency or allow the reduction of the dose. The harmful interactions can increase the incidence of adverse reactions and cause a reduction of the effects or results contrary to those expected.^[109]

Critically ill patients frequently receive multidrug regimens with the goal of providing pharmacotherapeutic support and cure of a medical condition. These patients are at risk for drug interactions (DIs) because of the complexity of this polypharmacy, as well as the frequent presence of altered organ function.^[113]

Polypharmacy refers to the routine use of five or more medications. But there are several different definitions where prescription containing two or more drugs is considered as polypharmacy. This includes OTC medications, prescription and/or traditional and complementary medicines. Polypharmacy is further divided into minor (2 - 4 drugs), moderate (4 - 5 drugs), major (6 - 9 drugs)

and Hyperpolypharmacy (≥ 10 drugs).^[14]

According to WHO the definition of ADR is ‘any response to a drug that is Noxious, unintended, and that occurs at Doses normally used in man for Prophylaxis, diagnosis or therapy of Diseases.’ Hence an ADR may include an exaggerated drug response, an unwanted Effect on an organ system, different from that being treated, an allergic or Hypersensitivity reaction, an Idiosyncratic reaction, or a drug Interaction that causes an increased or diminished response^[15]

Drug-Drug interactions (DDI) in patients receiving multi-drug therapy are of wide concern. Such interactions are an important cause of adverse drug reactions and may lead to an increased risk of hospitalization and higher health care costs. Seriousness and severity of Drug-Drug interactions are Hospitalization, Life-threatening and Death.

Four steps to manage a drug interaction

- Avoid the combination.
- Adjust the dose.
- Monitor the patient.
- Continue the medication if, the interaction is not clinically significant

Prevention of drug-drug interaction

The number of drugs used to treat patients must be minimized to reduce the incidence of potential drug-drug interactions, and adherence difficulties while at the same time minimizing the costs.

Consequences of Drug-Drug Interactions

There are 3 possible outcomes during drug-drug interactions.

- One (drug) may intensify the effects of other
- One may reduce the effects of other.
- The combination may produce a new response, but not seen when either of the drug is given alone.^[16]

The mechanisms of interactions can be subdivided into those that involve the pharmacokinetics of a drug, and those that are pharmacodynamics.

PHARMACOKINETIC INTERACTIONS:

Pharmacokinetic interactions are those that can affect the processes by which drugs are absorbed, distributed, metabolized and excreted (the so called ADME interactions).

Drug absorption interactions:

For drugs that are given long-term, in multiple doses (e.g. the oral anticoagulants) the rate of absorption is usually unimportant, provided the total amount of drug absorbed is not markedly altered. On the other hand for drugs that are given as single doses, intended to be absorbed rapidly (e.g. hypnotics or analgesics), where a rapidly achieved high

concentration is needed, a reduction in the rate of absorption may result in failure to achieve an adequate effect.

1. Effects of changes in gastrointestinal PH
2. Adsorption, chelation and other complexing mechanisms
3. Changes in gastrointestinal motility
4. Induction or inhibition of drug transporter proteins
5. Malabsorption caused by drugs

Drug distribution:

Some drugs are totally dissolved in the plasma water, but many others are transported with some proportion of their molecules in solution and the rest bound to plasma proteins, particularly the albumins.

The extent of this binding varies enormously but some drugs are extremely highly bound.

1. Protein-binding interactions.
2. Induction or inhibition of drug transport proteins.

Metabolism (biotransformation):

Although a few drugs are cleared from the body simply by being excreted unchanged in the urine, most are chemically altered within the body to less lipid- soluble compounds, which are more easily excreted by the kidneys. If this were not so, many drugs would persist in the body and continue to exert their effects for a long time. This chemical change is called ‘metabolism’, ‘biotransformation’, ‘biochemical degradation or sometimes ‘detoxification’.

1. Changes in first-pass metabolism
2. Enzyme induction
3. Enzyme inhibition
4. Genetic factors in drug metabolism
5. Cytochrome P450 iso-enzymes and predicting drug
6. Interactions

Drug excretion interaction.

- (a) Changes in urinary pH
- (b) Changes in active renal tubular excretion
- (c) Changes in renal blood flow
- (d) Biliary excretion and the entero-hepatic shunt

PHARMACODYNAMIC INTERACTIONS

Pharmacodynamic interactions are those where the effects of one drug are changed by the presence of another drug at its site of action. Sometimes the drugs directly compete for particular receptors (e.g. beta2 agonists, such as salbutamol, and beta blockers, such as propranolol) but often the reaction is more indirect and involves interference with physiological mechanisms. These interactions are much less easy to classify neatly than those of a pharmacokinetic type.

i. Additive interactions:

If two drugs that have the same pharmacological effect are given together the effects can be additive interaction.

ii. Synergism interaction:

An interaction between 2 or more drugs that cause's total effect of the drugs to be greater than the sum of the individual effects of each drug

iii. Antagonistic or opposing:

In contrast to additive interactions, there are some pairs of drugs with activities that are opposed to one another.^[17]

Based on profile of medications prescribed, the DDIs are identified and classified. According to severity, potential DDIs are classified as

1. MAJOR the effects are potentially life threatening or capable of causing permanent damage.
2. MODERATE The effects may cause deterioration in patients clinical Status and additional treatment or extension of hospital stay
3. MINOR: The effects are usually mild.

Drug interactions may lead to adverse drug reactions (ADR) that can be severe enough to necessitate hospitalization and increased health care costs. About 5% of all the ADR's in the hospital are caused by DDI, the majority of which are avoidable.^[104]

The Role of Pharmacist in Management of Drug Interaction

Clinical pharmacist can play an important role in the critical care unit in reducing and avoiding these pDDIs. The population in critical care unit have multiple co-morbidities which often require high-risk medications and need of time sensitive medication decisions. Routine ward rounds, frequent monitoring of drugs and lab data, intervening and assisting the physician to select drugs and dosage forms reduces such pDDIs.

The clinical pharmacist, along with the prescriber has a duty to ensure that patients are aware of the risk of Side effects and a suitable course of action. With their detailed knowledge of Medicine, clinical pharmacists have the ability to relate unexpected symptoms experienced by patients to possible adverse effects of their drug therapy. The Practice in clinical pharmacy also ensures that drug Interactions are minimized by avoiding drugs with Potential side effects in susceptible patients. Thus, clinical Pharmacist has a major role to play in relation to Prevention, detection, and reporting drug Interactions.^[19]

Pharmacists have an important role in decreasing medication misuse through collaborative drug therapy. This role is not new for pharmacists. Studies demonstrate that pharmacist

recommendations can prevent medication errors and minimize adverse effects. Other studies have shown that pharmacist recommendations can decrease the cost of therapy and improve outcomes.^[20]

WHY IN CRITICAL CARE UNIT PATIENTS ONLY

ICU is a specialized branch of medicine dealing with diagnosis, management and follow up of critically ill or injured patients. It requires input from other branches of medicine on various issues.^[21] Patients in intensive care unit are prescribed large numbers of drugs, highlighting the need to study potential

Drug-Drug Interactions in this environment.

Intensive care unit (ICU) patients are especially at increased risk to the development of drug interactions, and this condition is complicated by disease severity and organ failure, both of which can alter the pharmacologic response to medications. The potential for development of drug-drug interactions increases not only with the number of medications in use, but also the number of physicians who treat the same patient and older age of patients in ICU are another risk factors that complicate the treatment process.^[22]

The hospitalized patients in intensive care unit (ICU) have a higher risk for developing drug interactions than patients from other care units. In addition to multiple drugs therapy, patients in the ICU presented a risk due to the severity of disease and organ failure. Drug interactions contribute to the incidence of adverse reactions in ICU and often constitute an unrecognized complication in pharmacotherapy.^[19]

Intensive care medicine provides great benefits to patients with life- threatening acute illness or trauma. These benefits are a consequence of advancements in diagnostic testing, technological interventions and pharmacotherapy. Critically ill-patients frequently receive multidrug regimens with the goal of providing pharmacotherapeutic support and cure of a medical condition. These patients are at risk for drug interactions (Dis) because of the complexity of this polypharmacy, as well as the frequent presence of altered organ function. Furthermore, elderly, critically ill patients are particularly vulnerable to AES from Dis because of the additional presence of multiple co morbid disease states.

About 5% of all adverse drug reactions in hospitals are caused by DDIs, and the majority of which are avoidable. With the increase in the number of patients. Multiple diseases, and complex therapeutic regimens, poly-pharmacy becomes unavoidable in ICU. Polypharmacy increases the risks of drug AEs,

especially the DBDIS, and that leads to elevated healthcare costs, morbidity and mortality. Within the context of above facts, it is important to investigate potential DDIs in ICUs.^[13]

AIM

The aim of the study is to assess the role of clinical pharmacist in identifying & reporting management of potential Drug-drug interactions among the patient admitted to Intensive care unit

OBJECTIVES

1. To evaluate potency of Drug-drug interaction in ICU patient
2. To evaluate the incidence of potential Drug-drug interactions in ICU patients
3. To identifying and Intervening Drug-drug interaction in prescription by clinical pharmacist and reporting to the physician so that adverse effects caused by Drug-drug interactions can be prevented

METHODOLOGY:

Study Duration: Study was carried out for a period of six months. (March to August 2024)

Study Design: A prospective Hospital based interventional study.

Study Site: The study was carried out at Intensive care units of Gulbarga institute of medical sciences (GIMS) Hospital Sedam road, Kalaburagi.

Source of Data: Data is being collected from case sheets of patient admitted in "Intensive care unit

STUDY CRITERIA

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Patients of ≥ 18 yrs. age and older

2. Patient with an ICU stay of at least 24hrs
3. Patient or there legal guardian must provide inform consent form for willing to participate in study

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Patient with terminally ill and with life expectancy of less than 48hrs who are receiving palliative care
2. Post-surgical ICU patients with short term monitoring
3. Patient with cognitive impairment
4. Patient or legal guardian who don't consent to participate in study will be exclude

STUDY PROCEDURE

A Prospective Interventional study is carried out after obtaining ethical clearance from Institutional Review Board (IRB) GIMS. The study is carried out for a period of 6 months in intensive care units of GIMS, Kalaburgi. The study is conducted by enrolling patients admitted to intensive care unit, by considering the study criteria. A written consent is taken from the enrolled patients /legal guardian. From the case sheets of the enrolled patient's demographic, data, reason for admission, comorbidities, and medical and medication history, medication chart is noted in a suitably designed data collection form. The DDIs is identified and analyzed by using micromedex data base. The identified DDIs are brought to the notice of the physician/prescriber/PGs and possible measures are taken to avoid the interactions. The action taken by the physician/prescriber for the suggestions given by the clinical pharmacist to avoid the DDIs is also been noted.

Results and Observations

Table No.1: Age wise distribution of patients

Age in years	Number of patients	Percentage
≤ 20	3	1.7
21—40	41	23.2
41—60	83	46.9
> 60	50	28.2
Total	177	100.0
Mean \pm SD	52.25 \pm 15.48	

Study observes that, majority of patients 83 (46.9%) were belongs to the age group of 41—60 years. Followed by 50 (28.2%) of patients were belongs to the age of >60 years, 41 (23.2%) of patients were belongs to the age group of 21—40 years and 3 (1.7%) of patients were belongs to the age of ≤ 20 years. The mean age of patients was 52.25 years

Fig no .1 Simple bar diagram represents age wise distribution of patients

Table No.2: Gender wise distribution of patients

Gender	Number of patients	Percentage
Males	99	55.9
Females	78	44.1
Total	177	100.0

Study observed that; Male patients were predominant in the study they were 99 (55.9%) and 78 (44.1%) of patients were females. Male to Female ratio was 1.3:1

Fig no .2 Pie chart presents gender wise distribution of patients

Table No.3: Habits wise distribution of patients

Habits	Number of patients	Percentage
Alcohol	46	25.9
Tobacco	9	5.8
Smoking	31	17.5
No habits	96	54.2
Total	177	100%

In the present study majority of patients 96 (54.2%) does not have any habits, 31 (17.5%) of patients had the habit of smoking, 46 (25.9%) of patients had the habit of alcohol and 9 (5.8%) of patients had the habit of chewing tobacco

Fig no .3 Bar diagram presents habits wise distribution of patients

Table No.4: Distribution of patients based on with or without

Co-morbidities

Co-morbid	Number of patients	Percentage
With Co-morbidities	126	71.2
Without Co-morbidities	51	28.8
Total	177	100.0

Study observed that; 126 (71.2%) of patients were observed with co-morbidities and 51 (28.8%) of patients were not observed any co-morbidities

Fig no .4 Pie diagram presents co-morbidities wise distribution of patients

Table No.5: Past history of disease wise distribution of patients

Past history of disease	No. of patients	Percentage
HYPERTENSION [HTN]	56	31.6
DIABETES MELLITUS [DM]	32	18.1
PNEUMONIA	32	18.1
CEREBROVASCULAR ACCIDENT [CVA]	30	17.0
ACUTE KIDNEY INJURY [AKI]	25	14.1
ANEMIA	25	14.1
GASTROENTRITIS [GE]	16	9.0
ISCHAEMIC HEART DISEASE [IHD]	13	7.3
RESPIRATORY DEPRESSION	13	7.3
CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE[CKD]	11	6.2
COPD	11	6.2
SEPTIC SHOCK	10	5.6
OP POISONING	8	4.5
CARDIOMYOPATHY	8	4.5
CELLULITIS	8	4.5
PANCREATITIS	7	4.0
GASTRITIS	6	3.4
SEPTIC ENCEPHALOPATHY	5	2.8
ALCOHOLIC LIVER DISEASE [ALD]	5	2.8
PULMONARY TUBERCULOSIS,	4	2.3
PARKINSONS DISEASE	4	2.3
DECOMPENSATED CLD,	3	1.7
CARCINOMA	3	1.7
RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS	3	1.7
SNAKE BITE	3	1.7
UROSEPSIS	3	1.7

Study observed that; majority of patient's 56 (31.6%) past history of disease was hypertension with other complications, each 32 (18.1) of patient's past history of disease were observed diabetes mellitus with complications and pneumonia respectively, 30 (17.0%) were CVA, each 25 (14.1%) were AKI and anemia respectively

Table No.6: Duration of hospital stay wise distribution of patients

Duration of hospital stay	No. of patients	Percentage
1—7 days (1 week)	142	80.2
8—14 days (2 weeks)	34	19.2
14—21 days (3 weeks)	1	0.6
Total	177	100.0

Study observed that; majority of patient's 142 (80.2%) duration of hospital stay was 1—7 days (1-week), followed by 34 (19.2%) of patient's duration of hospital stay was 8—14 days (2 weeks) and 1 (0.6%) of patient's duration of hospital stay was 14—21 days (3 weeks)

Fig no .5 Bar diagram represents duration of hospital stay wise distribution of patients

Table No.7: Distribution of patients based on Number of drugs prescribed drugs

Number of drugs Prescribed	Number of patients	Percentage
5—10	85	48.0
11—15	78	44.1
>15	14	7.9
Total	177	100.0
Mean \pm SD	10.94 \pm 3.17	----

Study observed that; majority of patients 85 (48.0%) were prescribed 5—10 drugs, 78 (44.1%) of patients were prescribed 11—15 drugs and 14 (7.9%) of patients were prescribed more than 15 drugs. Minimum drugs prescribed a patient 5, maximum drugs prescribed a patient 23 and average drugs prescribed in the study was 10.94 drugs

Fig no 6. Bar diagram presents number of drugs prescribed wise distribution of patients

Table No.8: Treatment prescription pattern wise distribution of patients

Prescription pattern	No. of patients	Percentage
ONDANSETRON [ONDAN]	138	78.0
PANTOPRAZOLE[PANTA]	122	68.9
CEFTRIAZONE[CEFTR]	86	48.6
ASPIRIN [ASPIR]	82	30.5
FUROSEMIDE [FUROS]	64	36.2
RANITIDINE [RANTA]	59	33.3
PIPERACILLIN +TAZOBACTUM[PIPTA]	57	32.2
PARACETAMOL[PARAC]	56	31.6
AMLODIPINE [AMLOD]	46	26.0
IPRATROPIUM,LEVOSALBUTAMOL [IPRAT+LSALBU+BUDES]	43	24.3
PHENYTOIN [PHENY]	41	23.2
MANNITOL [MANNI]	39	22.0
MEROPENEM [MEROP]	28	15.8
LACTULOSE [LACTU]	28	15.8
THIAMINE [THIAM]	28	15.8
SODIUM BICARBONATE [NAHCO3]	28	15.8
NORADRENALINE [NORAD]	26	14.7
AMOXICILLIN CLAVULANATE[AMOXC]	23	13.0
TRAMADOL [TRAMA]	23	13.0
LOW MOLECULAR WEIGHT HEPARIN [LMWH]	22	12.4
3% SODIUM CHLORIDE [3%NACL]	19	10.7
AZITHROMYCIN [AZITH]	18	10.2

COBALAMIN [VITB12]	18	10.2
LORAZEPAM [LORAZ]	16	9.0
SPIRONOLACTONE [SPIRO]	16	9.0
LEVOFLOXACIN [LFLOX]	15	8.5
METFORMIN [METFO]	14	7.9
DEXAMETHASONE [DEXAM]	12	6.8
LEVETIRACETAM [LEVIP]	12	6.8
POTASSIUM CHLORIDE [POTCL]	12	6.8
CIPROFLOXACIN [CFLOX]	10	5.6

Study observed that; majority of treatment prescription 138 (78.0%) was ONDAN, followed by PANTA 122 (68.9%), CEFTR 86 (48.6%), FUROS 64 (36.2%)

Table No.9: Distribution according to number of Drug- drug interaction per patients

Number of DDI	Number of patients	Percentage
DDI 1	59	33.3
DDI 2	38	21.5
DDI 3	19	10.7
DDI 4	22	12.5
DDI 5	11	6.2
DDI 6	17	9.6
DDI 7	11	6.2
Total	177	100.0
Mean \pm SD	2.90 \pm 1.94	---

Study observed that; All 177 (100.0%) of patients was observed DDIs, minimum 1 DDI patients were seen 59 (33.3%) and maximum 7 DDI patients were 11 (6.2%). The average DDIs was 2.90 drugs. Total number of interaction of drugs was 514

Fig no .7 Bar diagram represent number of DDIs per patients

Table No.10: Classification of DDIs according to severity

Severity	Number of DDI	Number of patients	Percentage
Minor	96	10	18.6%
Moderate	172	34	33.46%
Major	246	133	47.86%
Total	514	177	100.0

Study observed that; majority of patients 133 – 246 (47.86%) were observed DDIs severity was major, 34 - 172(33.46%) of patients were seen moderate DDIs and 10 - 96(18.6%) of patients were seen minor DDIs

Fig no .8 Bar diagram presents classification of DDIs according to severity

Table No.11: Most common drug involved in DDIs

The following drugs were found to be most interacting

Name of the drug	Number of interactions	Percentage
ONDANSETRON [ONDAN]	54	30.5
PHENYTOIN [PHENY]	51	28.8
FUROSEMIDE[FUROS]	31	17.5
RANITIDINE [RANTA]	26	14.7
TRAMADOL [TRAMA]	21	11.9
CLOPIDOGREL [CLOPI]	18	10.2
PANTOPRAZOLE [PANTA]	13	7.3
METFORMIN [METFOR]	12	6.8
ASPIRIN [ASPIR]	10	5.6
METRONIDAZOLE [METRO]	9	5.1
HUMAN INSULIN [HATRA]	8	4.5
RAMIPRIL [RAMIP]	7	4.0
AZITHROMYCIN [AZITH]	6	3.4
ATORVASTATIN [ATORV]	5	2.8
DIGOXIN [DIGOX]	5	2.8
LEVOFLOXACIN [LFLOX]	5	2.8

Study observed that; the most common drug involved in DDI was ONDAN i-e 54 (30.5%) of patients, followed by 51 (28.8%) of patients had seen the most common drug involved in DDI was PHENY, 31 (17.5%) of patients had seen the common drug involved in DDI was FUROS,

Table No.12: Most common pairs of drug involved in DDIs

The following pairs of drugs were found to be commonly interacting

Sl.no	Drug combinations	No of time observed
1	ONDANSETRON +METRONIDAZOLE	16
2	ASPIRIN + FUROSEMIDE	15
3	ASPIRIN + PHENYTOIN	15
4	TRAMADOL + ONDANSETRON	15
5	ATORVASTATIN + PHENYTOIN	13
6	PHENYTOIN + RANITIDINE	12
7	ASPIRIN + CLOPIDOGREL	10
8	LEVOLOFLOXACIN + ONDANSETRON	10
9	AZITHROMYCIN + ONDANSETRON	9
10	CIPROFLOXACIN + ONDANSETRON	8

Table No.13: Comparison of duration of hospital stays with DDI's

Duration of hospital stay	No. of patients	DDI's	Average
1—7 days (1 week)	142	358	2.52
8—14 days (2 weeks)	34	151	4.44
14—21 days (3 weeks)	1	5	5.00
Total	177	514	2.90
ANOVA Test, P-value	F = 12.472, P = 0.001, HS		

Study reveals that; there was statistically significant association of duration of hospital stays and DDI's ($P < 0.001$). More number of days of hospital stays patients was observed more numbers of DDI's

Fig no.9 :Bar diagram represents comparison of duration of hospital stay with DDI's

Table No.14: Distribution of DDI's according to management suggestions by Clinical pharmacist to prescribers /physicians

Suggestions	No. of interactions (DDI)	Percentage
Suggestions not accepted	383	74.5
Suggestions accepted	131	25.5
Total	514	100.0

In the study out of 514 DDI's (interactions), 383 (74.5%) of DDI's not accepted followed the suggestions of clinical pharmacist and 131 (25.5%) of DDI's accepted followed the suggestions of clinical pharmacist

Fig no.10: Pie chart presents Distribution of DDI's according to management suggestions by Clinical pharmacist to prescribers /physicians

CONCLUSION:

The study aimed to assess the role of clinical pharmacists in identifying, reporting, and managing potential drug-drug interactions (DDIs) among ICU patients. With the increasing complexity of therapeutic regimens in critically ill patients, the risk of DDIs is increases, and the involvement of clinical pharmacists is crucial

Among a total of 177 patients included in study from the Intensive Care Unit (ICU) at GIMS hospital. The majority of the patients were male (55.9%), with a mean age of 52.25 years, and the most prevalent age group being 41-60 years. Hypertension (31.6%) and diabetes mellitus (18.1%) were the most common comorbidities.

Key findings from the study revealed:

- Polypharmacy: The average number of drugs prescribed per patient was 10.94, with 48% of patients receiving 5-10 drugs. The risk of DDIs increased with the number of medications prescribed.
- Prevalence of DDIs: All 177 patients identified at least one DDI, with an average of 2.90 interactions per patient. The total number of identified DDIs was 514, with major interactions accounting for 47.86% of the cases.
- Severity of DDIs: A significant proportion of DDIs were categorized as major (47.86%), followed by moderate (33.46%) and minor (18.6%) interactions. Common Drugs Involved in DDIs: Ondansetron,

phenytoin, and furosemide were the most frequently interacting drugs, highlighting the importance of vigilant monitoring of these medications in ICU settings

- Duration of stay in hospital: Study reveals that; there was statistically significant association of duration of hospital stays and DDI's . More number of days of hospital stays patients was observed more numbers of DDI's

The study concludes that the presence of a clinical pharmacist in the ICU can play a pivotal role in the early identification and management of potential DDIs, thus improves patient outcomes. The clinical pharmacist's interventions, including adjustments in drug regimens, dose alterations, and frequent monitoring, were essential in minimizing the adverse effects caused by DDIs. This collaborative approach between clinical pharmacists and physicians led to a more optimized and safer medication therapy.

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